

LEARNING FOREIGN EXPERIENCE AND EXPANDING SERVICES IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM

Fergana Polytechnic Institute

Assistant **B. Arzimatov**

Annotation: Large-scale reforms have been implemented in Uzbekistan to increase the service sector, in particular, the volume of tourism services. In particular: in order to improve the quality of tourism services, regulatory and legal documents, standards and new requirements were developed, management structures were improved. In this article, we can discuss about information the learning foreign experience and expanding services in the field of tourism.

Keywords: learning, foreign experience, expand service, tourism, process, network, employment.

In turn, the further development of the national tourism industry and the expansion of the flow of foreign tourists and the export of tourism services, the creation of new jobs in the network, the increase of the employment level of the population, the increase of the number of hotels, other means of accommodation for tourists, and the number of subjects engaged in tourism activities study of economic aspects of their growth and managementimprovement is one of the urgent tasks of today.

We can see the following specific aspects in the international practice of tourism. Firstly, the consumption of tourist products and services by tourists, secondly, by tour companies, producers of tourism products and sellers of services (including guests), thirdly, state bodies that carry out tourism activity licensing, standardization and certification of tourism products, fourthly, state companies that protect tourist organizations and social organizations that regulate interactions between tourists can be seen.

The parties involved in this relationship may rely on laws and regulations, but in many countries the main effort is to regulate the "travel company-state" side. First of all, this is done through licensing of tourist activities. In countries where there is no licensing, there is legislation that regulates "tourist-tour company" relations, the main task of which is to protect the rights of tourist consumers and to constantly increase the responsibility of travel companies for tourism products and other services. Here, it is important for the tourist to have information about the conditions of travel, the existence of standards and laws for the implementation and formalization of tourism. Instructions are developed for this. For example, Germany "Your rights travel with you" was developed by the Ministry of Justice and approved by law. It details the rules for resolving controversial issues. But in almost every country of the world, there are mutual relations between travel agencies and the state and tourists, which are resolved through professional organizations. For example, "Association of Tourist Agents" operates in Russia. "Association of Private Tourist Organizations" was also established in Uzbekistan (1998). But in almost every country of the world, there are mutual relations between travel agencies and the state and tourists, which are resolved through professional organizations. For example, "Association of Tourist Agents" operates in Russia. "Association of Private Tourist Organizations" was also established in Uzbekistan (1998). But in almost every country of the world, there are mutual relations between travel agencies and the state and tourists, which are resolved through professional organizations. For example, "Association of Tourist Agents" operates in Russia. "Association of Private Tourist Organizations" was also established in Uzbekistan (1998).

Places that increase the interest of foreign tourists are sufficiently organized in Uzbekistan. However, they should be presented in such a way that they really arouse interest in tourists and express their desire to visit Uzbekistan, which is an ancient country like China, Mexico, and Japan. According to the results of the surveys, the greatest interest of tourists from the cities of Uzbekistan is Bukhara (35%), Samarkand (24%), Khiva (22%), Nukus and Termez (9%), Tashkent (4%) and other

cities (10%). let's go According to the survey results, 45 percent of tourists expressed interest in folk music and dances, national clothes and customs, 34 percent in national cuisine, and 26 percent in handicrafts and souvenirs.

Most of the tourists do not have a complete impression of the country before coming to Uzbekistan. After the tour, 79-80 percent of them return to their country and decide to study materials about Uzbekistan, learn more about its people, culture, customs and economy.

We see that such a great interest in the republic is not only for excursions, historical and cultural monuments, but also because of the good service. According to the survey results, we see that 81% of foreign tourists are completely satisfied with the provided services, 15.1% are partially satisfied, 1.9% are not at all satisfied, and 1.2% could not answer.

Of course, the increase in the flow of foreign tourists and the formation of the republic's image as an international tourist center are directly related to the easing of border, customs, visa and other formalities, as well as guaranteeing the safety of tourists.

We see that the tourism infrastructure is very unevenly distributed on the territory of Uzbekistan. 40 percent of the total potential of tourist infrastructure is collected in Tashkent city and Tashkent region alone. Therefore, it is desirable to further develop the types of tour routes and forms of spending time that can attract foreign tourists in other regions of our republic. For example, ecological routes are expanding in the countries of the world. Such resources in Uzbekistan include Charvoq reservoir in Jizzakh district, Fergana valley and other places. Natural parks, casinos and bars, golf clubs are new sources of foreign currency income. As the experience of the countries of the world shows, 40-50 percent of the gross income received is from the service sector, falls into the spheres of commerce and entertainment. Some tour companies of our republic offer exotic forms of travel ("Camel travel", "Yurta - war - massaget"), historical tourism ("Heritage of Amir Temur"), mountain tourism ("Beauty of Chimyon"), archaeological tourism

("Ancient Termiz"), ecological tourism ("Aydar kol" beach, etc.) have also been developed.

As can be seen from the above information, in my opinion, our republic will have the opportunity to increase the number of tourists by 1500-1800 thousand people in the coming years. Of course, the organization of special regional itineraries developed by tour operators plays a big role in this, for example, introducing the large vineyards in the Altiariq region and enlightening the rural life of the population will arouse interest in the beaches.

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